

MEASURES AIMED AT TREATMENT AND PREVENTION OF FLUTTERING
ARRHYTHMIA IN A MODERN INTERPRETATION

Shernazarov Sardor

Samarkand State Medical University

DKTF (Faculty of Postgraduate Education)

Department of Therapy, Cardiology and Functional Diagnostics

Daniyorov Shahzod

Samarkand State Medical University

DKTF (Faculty of Postgraduate Education)

Department of Therapy, Cardiology and Functional Diagnostics

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10928082>

Abstract. Atrial fibrillation (atrial fibrillation) is a type of heart rhythm disorder characterized by a frequent and chaotic beating rhythm. With this pathology, there is a violation of blood circulation, which affects all human organs and systems. In a healthy body, the heart rate can also increase or, conversely, decrease. All this is a normal adaptation of the heart to current loads. Thus, heart rate increases during intense physical activity and decreases, respectively, during rest. This process is completely physiological and is necessary to ensure adequate blood flow to the muscles.

Key words: Arrhythmia, rhythmic arrhythmia, swing arrhythmia, treatment and prevention.

МЕРОПРИЯТИЯ, НАПРАВЛЕННЫЕ НА ЛЕЧЕНИЕ И ПРОФИЛАКТИКУ
ТРЕПЕТАЮЩЕЙ АРИТМИИ В СОВРЕМЕННОЙ ИНТЕРПРЕТАЦИИ

Аннотация. Мерцательная аритмия (мерцательная аритмия) — вид нарушения сердечного ритма, характеризующийся частым и хаотичным ритмом сокращений. При этой патологии происходит нарушение кровообращения, что затрагивает все органы и системы человека. В здоровом организме частота сердечных сокращений также может увеличиваться или, наоборот, уменьшаться. Все это нормальная адаптация сердца к текущим нагрузкам. Таким образом, частота сердечных сокращений увеличивается при интенсивных физических нагрузках и соответственно снижается во время отдыха. Этот процесс полностью физиологичен и необходим для обеспечения адекватного притока крови к мышцам.

Ключевые слова: Аритмия, ритмическая аритмия, маховая аритмия, лечение и профилактика.

However, with a pathological change in the heart rhythm, regardless of the intensity of the load, an increase and decrease in the frequency of beats occurs. Arrhythmia can occur both during physical activity and in a state of physical and emotional rest. In some cases, the heart rate can reach up to 600 beats per minute, which is a serious threat to life.

Without proper treatment, the pathology can cause angina pectoris, thromboembolism, ischemic stroke or even cardiac arrest.

Symptoms of atrial fibrillation

It can be difficult to diagnose the disease independently, because atrial fibrillation is often asymptomatic. In this case, the pathology is determined by diagnosing electrocardiogram. If there are symptoms, the patient feels a "wave" or "pounding" heart, shortness of breath, weakness, suffocation, heaviness and pain in the chest, sometimes a feeling of fear, complains of sweating. In some cases, an attack of arrhythmia can be accompanied by a sharp drop in blood pressure, followed by loss of consciousness and the threat of death.

Causes of atrial fibrillation

Modern medicine distinguishes two groups of causes of atrial fibrillation: organic and functional. The first group is directly related to cardiovascular pathologies. The second - with disturbances in the functioning of other organs and systems.

Organic causes include:

- dysfunction of coronary arteries;
- arterial hypertension;
- heart disease;
- atherosclerotic heart disease;
- myocarditis;
- ischemic disease;
- heart failure;
- sinus node pathology;
- consequences of heart surgery.

The most common functional reasons:

- lack of magnesium and potassium in the body;
- stress;
- abuse of alcohol, caffeine and energy drinks;
- pathologies of the thyroid gland;

- blood diseases;
- physical or emotional stress that exceeds the body's reserves.

Diagnosis of atrial fibrillation

Disease diagnosis is carried out by highly qualified specialists with many years of experience in the field of cardiology. During the research, high-precision equipment that meets all the requirements of modern medicine is used.

The first visit to the clinic begins with the collection of anamnesis (medical history). For this purpose, the patient is interviewed and carefully examined. After the initial diagnosis, the patient is sent to additional laboratory and instrumental studies to confirm it.

Holter ECG is the main method for detecting arrhythmia. In this study, a 24-hour electrocardiogram is recorded, which allows to identify factors that can change the normal heartbeat.

Echocardiography is an ultrasound examination of the heart muscle.

A stress ECG is a study in which conditions that cause rhythm disturbances are triggered.

Bicycle ergometry is a study that uses additional physical activity (called "cycling").

The treadmill test is a test in which the patient's EKG is recorded while walking on a treadmill.

The tilt test is an examination performed on an orthostatic table, in which data is recorded when the body changes its position.

Lifting tests - studying during squats, running and other physical exercises.

An endocardial ECG is a type of diagnosis in which catheters are inserted into the heart to record internal and external data.

General blood and urine tests - laboratory tests to determine the presence of concomitant pathologies (for example, anemia).

Therapeutic treatment of atrial fibrillation

There are two ways to treat atrial fibrillation - conservative and surgical.

Conservative therapy is aimed at preventing or stopping the attack of arrhythmia. For this, doctors choose optimal doses of antiarrhythmic drugs. Beta blockers, slow calcium channel blockers, or cardiac glycosides may be used to control normal heart rates.

Anticoagulant drugs are used for arrhythmias accompanied by the formation of blood clots. If atrial fibrillation is the result of another heart disease, therapy is aimed not only at eliminating the symptom, but also at fighting the main cause.

It should be remembered that only a qualified cardiologist can choose the right treatment that will bring positive results.

Surgical treatment of atrial fibrillation

If therapeutic treatment is ineffective or in advanced stages of atrial fibrillation, the patient may require surgical intervention.

Implantation of a pacemaker affecting the heart rhythm.

Implantation of a cardioverter-defibrillator that monitors and stops cardiac arrhythmia.

Heart surgery that eliminates the main cause of arrhythmia (removal of heart defects, aneurysms, valvular defects, etc).

REFERENCES

1. Andryev S. et al. Experience with the use of memantine in the treatment of cognitive disorders //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D11. – C. 282-288.
2. Antsiborov S. et al. Association of dopaminergic receptors of peripheral blood lymphocytes with a risk of developing antipsychotic extrapyramidal diseases //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D11. – C. 29-35.
3. Asanova R. et al. Features of the treatment of patients with mental disorders and cardiovascular pathology //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 545-550.
4. Begbudiyeu M. et al. Integration of psychiatric care into primary care //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 551-557.
5. Bo'Riyev B. et al. Features of clinical and psychopathological examination of young children //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 558-563.
6. Borisova Y. et al. Concomitant mental disorders and social functioning of adults with high-functioning autism/asperger syndrome //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D11. – C. 36-41.
7. Ivanovich U. A. et al. Efficacy and tolerance of pharmacotherapy with antidepressants in non-psychotic depressions in combination with chronic brain ischemia //Science and Innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 12. – C. 409-414.
8. Karshiyev Z. et al. The degree of adaptation to psychogenic effects in social life in patients with psychogenic asthma //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D11. – C. 295-302.

9. Konstantinova O. et al. Clinical and psychological characteristics of patients with alcoholism with suicidal behavior //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D11. – C. 399-404.
10. Konstantinova O. et al. Experience in the use of thiamine (vitamin B1) megadose in the treatment of korsakov-type alcoholic encephalopathy //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 564-570.
11. Kosolapov V. et al. Modern strategies to help children and adolescents with anorexia nervosa syndrome //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 571-575.
12. Lomakin S. et al. Biopsychosocial model of internet-dependent behavior. Risk factors for the formation of the internet //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 205-211.
13. Lomakin S. et al. Features of electroencephalographic disorders in patients with mental disorders due to brain damage or dysfunction //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 367-372.
14. Lomakin S. et al. Socio-demographic, personal and clinical characteristics of relatives of patients with alcoholism //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 278-283.
15. Lukasheva A. et al. Psychosomatic relationships in different age groups in patients with facial dermatosis //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D11. – C. 289-294.
16. Malakhov A. et al. Modern views on the treatment and rehabilitation of patients with dementia //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 322-329.
17. Malakhov A. et al. Problems of prevention of socially dangerous behavior by individuals with mental disorders //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D11. – C. 405-412.
18. Nematilayevna S. D. et al. Psychological factors for the formation of aggressive behavior in the youth environment //Science and Innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 12. – C. 404-408.
19. Nikolaevich R. A. et al. Comparative effectiveness of treatment of somatoform diseases in psychotherapeutic practice //Science and Innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 12. – C. 898-903.
20. Novikov A. et al. Alcohol dependence and manifestation of autoaggressive behavior in patients of different types //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D11. – C. 413-419.
21. Ochilov U. et al. Factors of alcoholic delirium patomorphosis //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 223-229.

22. Ochilov U. et al. The main forms of aggressive manifestations in the clinic of mental disorders of children and adolescents and factors affecting their occurrence //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D11. – C. 42-48.
23. Ochilov U. et al. The question of the features of clinical and immunological parameters in the diagnosis of juvenile depression with" subpsychotic" symptoms //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 218-222.
24. Pachulia Y. et al. Assessment of the effect of psychopathic disorders on the dynamics of withdrawal syndrome in synthetic cannabinoid addiction //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 240-244.
25. Pachulia Y. et al. Neurobiological indicators of clinical status and prognosis of therapeutic response in patients with paroxysmal schizophrenia //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 385-391.
26. Pogosov A. et al. Multidisciplinary approach to the rehabilitation of patients with somatized personality development //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 245-251.
27. Pogosov A. et al. Rational choice of pharmacotherapy for senile dementia //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 230-235.
28. Pogosov S. et al. Gnostic disorders and their compensation in neuropsychological syndrome of vascular cognitive disorders in old age //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 258-264.
29. Pogosov S. et al. Prevention of adolescent drug abuse and prevention of yatrogenia during prophylaxis //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 392-397.
30. Pogosov S. et al. Psychogenetic properties of drug patients as risk factors for the formation of addiction //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 186-191.
31. Prostyakova N. et al. Changes in the postpsychotic period after acute polymorphic disorder //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 356-360.
32. Prostyakova N. et al. Issues of professional ethics in the treatment and management of patients with late dementia //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 158-165.
33. Prostyakova N. et al. Sadness and loss reactions as a risk of forming a relationship together //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 252-257.
34. Prostyakova N. et al. Strategy for early diagnosis with cardiovascular diseaseisomatized mental disorders //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 166-172.

35. Rotanov A. et al. Comparative effectiveness of treatment of somatoform diseases in psychotherapeutic practice //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 267-272.
36. Rotanov A. et al. Diagnosis of depressive and suicidal spectrum disorders in students of a secondary special education institution //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D11. – C. 309-315.
37. Rotanov A. et al. Elderly epilepsy: neurophysiological aspects of non-psychotic mental disorders //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 192-197.
38. Rotanov A. et al. Social, socio-cultural and behavioral risk factors for the spread of hiv infection //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D11. – C. 49-55.
39. Rotanov A. et al. Suicide and epidemiology and risk factors in oncological diseases //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 398-403.
40. Sedenkov V. et al. Clinical and socio-demographic characteristics of elderly patients with suicide attempts //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 273-277.
41. Sedenkov V. et al. Modern methods of diagnosing depressive disorders in neurotic and affective disorders //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 361-366.
42. Sedenkova M. et al. Basic principles of organizing gerontopsychiatric assistance and their advantages //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D11. – C. 63-69.
43. Sedenkova M. et al. Features of primary and secondary cognitive functions characteristic of dementia with delirium //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D11. – C. 56-62.
44. Sedenkova M. et al. The possibility of predicting the time of formation and development of alcohol dependence: the role of genetic risk, family weight and its level //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 173-178.
45. Shamilov V. et al. Disorders of decision-making in the case of depression: clinical evaluation and correlation with eeg indicators //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 198-204.
46. Sharapova D. et al. Clinical and socio-economic effectiveness of injectable long-term forms of atypical antipsychotics in schizophrenia //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 290-295.
47. Sharapova D., Shernazarov F., Turayev B. Prevalence of mental disorders in children and adolescents with cancer and methods of their treatment //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 373-378.

48. Sharapova D., Shernazarov F., Turayev B. Social characteristics of patients with schizophrenia for a long time in combination with exogenous-organic diseases of the brain //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 284-289.
49. Solovyova Y. et al. Protective-adaptive complexes with codependency //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D11. – C. 70-75.
50. Solovyova Y. et al. Suicide prevention in adolescents with mental disorders //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D11. – C. 303-308.
51. Solovyova Y. et al. The relevance of psychotic disorders in the acute period of a stroke //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 212-217.
52. Spirkina M. et al. Integrated approach to correcting neurocognitive defects in schizophrenia //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D11. – C. 76-81.
53. Sultanov S. et al. Changes in alcohol behavior during the covid-19 pandemic and beyond //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 302-309.
54. Farrukh S. ORGANIZATION OF DIGITALIZED MEDICINE AND HEALTH ACADEMY AND ITS SIGNIFICANCE IN MEDICINE //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. Special Issue 8. – C. 493-499.
55. Sultanov S. et al. Depression and post-traumatic stress disorder in patients with alcoholism after the covid-19 pandemic //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D11. – C. 420-429.
56. Sultanov S. et al. Long-term salbi effects of the covid-19 pandemic on the health of existing residents of alcohol addiction //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D11. – C. 430-438.
57. Sultanov S. et al. The impact of the covid-19 pandemic on the mental state of people with alcohol addiction syndrome //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 296-301.
58. Uskov A. et al. Atypical anorexia nervosa: features of preposition and premorbid //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 310-315.
59. Uskov A. et al. Evaluation of the effectiveness of supportive therapy in the practice of outpatient treatment of schizophrenia with long term atypical antipsychotics //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 316-321.
60. Uskov A. et al. Modern methods of therapeutic fasting as a way to overcome the pharmacoresistance of mental pathology //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 179-185.

61. Uskov A. et al. Psychological peculiarities of social adaptation in paranoid schizophrenia //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D12. – C. 379-384.
62. Viktorova N. et al. Formation of rehabilitation motivation in the conditions of the medical and rehabilitation department of a psychiatric hospital //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D11. – C. 82-89.
63. Viktorova N. et al. Opportunities for comprehensive psychometric assessment of anxiety states in late-age dementia //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D11. – C. 90-96.

MODERN SCIENCE
& RESEARCH